

On the Co-separation Study of Acid-insoluble Pyrophosphates of Rare Elements

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Distribution study with Sc^{46} and UX_1 as guest ions and Ce(IV) and Zr as host components shows that both Ce(IV) and Zr take up scandium and UX_1 (thorium) through mixed crystal formation when the hosts are precipitated as pyrophosphate. In all these cases the study has been extended from tracer level to finite concentration of the tracer ion. In the case of scandium attempt has been made to find out the limiting concentration of the tracer ion. It has been observed that up to the limiting concentration of the guest ion, λ values remain constant, but beyond it λ value, though constant at a particular concentration, assumes diminishing trend as the concentration of the guest ion is increased. Data have been discussed in the light of the observation of Hahn⁶ and Khlopin⁵.

Insolubility of the pyrophosphate of scandium in mineral acids has been utilised by us in finding out a method of determining scandium by radiometric procedure with P^{32} as a measuring indicator in presence of rare earths¹. With a view to ascertaining any morphological analogy existing among these insoluble pyrophosphates, a study of the co-separation with Sc^{46} and UX_1 as guests and Ce(IV) and Zr pyrophosphates as hosts was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sc^{46} was supplied by the Philips Dupher, who prepared it by (n, γ) reaction on natural scandium. The concentration of scandium in tracer scale was computed from supplier's report on the specific activity of Sc^{46} . Carrier-free UX_1 was prepared in the laboratory from uranium, of G. R.-E. Merck quality. Ceric sulphate used was of AnalaR variety. Zirconium nitrate was of spectrochemical purity supplied by the Johnson Matthey & Co, England. Sodium pyrophosphate was prepared by taking a known amount of disodium hydrogen phosphate and heating it to 600° for 6 hours². Conversion to pyrophosphate was 98.5%. Pyrophosphate, thus prepared, was preserved in a desiccator and a portion was taken at the time of study and dissolved in water; different portions of the solution were dropped from a burette into the solution ($0.5N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$) containing the host and the guest under constant stirring. An aliquot portion of the solution was taken by a pipette with a filter paper cap at the mouth (to prevent entrance of any solid matter). Ce(IV) was estimated iodometrically and zirconium was estimated as pyrophosphate in the usual way. The liquid counter was found very suitable for activity measurements. Heterogeneous distribution factor (λ)³ was calculated as reported earlier⁷.

1. Purkayastha and Verneker, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 180.
2. Audrath, "Inorganic Synthesis", Vol III, McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc., 1950, p. 100.
3. Doerner and Hoakins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 662.
4. "Applied Radiochemistry", Cornell University Press, New York, 1936.
5. *Doklady Akad. Nauk., S. S. S. R.*, 1949, 65, 861; 1950, 71, 689.

TABLE I

Co-separation of UX₁ by ceric pyrophosphate at room temp. (28°).

%Ce(IV) pptd.	%UX ₁ uptake.	λ.	%Ce(IV) pptd.	%UX ₁ uptake.	λ.
	Th = tracer conc.			Th = 1.25 × 10 ⁻⁴ M.	
11.45	26.10	2.56	22.5	41.0	2.07
18.60	42.90	2.72	27.2	48.6	2.10
30.30	53.70	2.01	32.2	53.6	1.97
39.30	65.30	2.12	43.6	69.0	2.02
		Av. 2.35			Av. 2.04

TABLE II

Co-separation of UX₁ by zirconium pyrophosphate at room temp.

%Zr pptd.	%UX ₁ uptake.	λ.	%Zr pptd.	%UX ₁ uptake.	λ.
	Th = tracer conc.			Th = 1.25 × 10 ⁻⁴ M.	
24.22	42.25	1.98	23.50	41.90	2.03
35.92	56.90	1.90	30.20	48.70	1.85
38.80	62.50	2.00	35.90	58.10	1.95
48.45	75.00	2.09	42.40	67.00	2.01
		Av. 1.99	51.50	79.00	2.15
					Av. 2.00

TABLE III

Co-separation of Sc⁴⁵ by zirconium pyrophosphate at room temp.

%Zr pptd.	%Sc uptake.	λ.	%Zr pptd.	%Sc uptake.	λ.
	Sc = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M.			Sc = 2.2 × 10 ⁻³ M.	
14.5	34.0	2.6	18.9	40.0	2.4
24.2	46.7	2.3	26.3	51.4	2.4
38.8	62.6	2.0	34.0	66.0	2.2
48.2	74.4	2.2			Av. 2.33
58.2	83.9	2.1			
		Av. 2.2			

TABLE IV

*Limit of the uptake of Sc⁴⁵ by ceric pyrophosphate at room temp.*Initial Ce(IV) conc = 3.3 × 10⁻²M.

Conc. of Sc.	%Ce(IV) pptd.	%Sc uptake.	λ.
1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M	13.75	21.30	1.57
	21.40	32.70	1.64
	32.40	41.30	1.36
	37.80	48.60	1.41
	45.60	58.40	1.44
	51.40	69.50	1.64
			Av. 1.51

TABLE IV (contd.)

Conc. of Sr .	%Ce(rv)pptd.	%Sr uptake.	λ .
$1.5 \times 10^{-7} M$	27.50	37.60	1.46
1.5×10^{-5}	24.50	35.90	1.58
	29.50	43.20	1.62
	48.56	64.50	1.56
			Av. 1.57
9.0×10^{-4}	26.14	36.75	1.50
3.7×10^{-3}	20.00	31.40	1.69
	29.54	40.90	1.50
	48.60	65.70	1.61
			Av. 1.60
9.0×10^{-3}	20.40	24.27	1.20
	28.50	35.00	1.10
	38.34	44.66	1.20
			Av. 1.16
1.8×10^{-2}	28.10	29.35	1.05

DISCUSSION

It has been found that from tracer level to finite concentration, the guest ion is taken up by zirconium and ceric pyrophosphates through mixed crystal formation. It brings in a third form of anomaly as defined by Hahn⁴ and Khlopin⁵. In the study of anomalous mixed crystals by Hahn⁴ in the uptake of lead (tracer) by alkali halides, there is a limiting concentration of the guest ion where alkali halide takes up lead through mixed crystal formation. The limit is reached at about 0.1 mole% of the tracer ion (lead)⁶. Hahn did not study what happened on further increasing the amount of the tracer ion. But in this case, up to 10 mole% of the tracer ion is accommodated easily in the host lattice. Even accommodation through mixed crystal formation up to 30 mole% of the guest ion has been observed. But the value of the partition factor is less (Table IV) unlike that of Khlopin and Merkulova⁵ in the study of uptake of radium and UX₂ by LaF₃ where the partition factor is increased on increasing the tracer-ion concentration. They⁵ explained the anomaly on the hypothesis that molecular mixed crystal formation was less probable at tracer level where the probability of simultaneous meeting of positively and negatively charged ions became less. Possibility of different complex-ion formation, which may lessen the partition factor at tracer level, was not, however, thought of by them. In a previous study⁷ in this laboratory on the uptake of thorium, yttrium, and europium by calcium oxalate, it was found that λ values remained constant up to a limiting concentration of the guest ion and there after it assumed a diminishing trend on increasing the concentration of the tracer ion. This diminishing trend at a finite concentration has been explained on the assumption that different complex ions do exist at higher concentrations

6. Wahl and Bonner, "Radioactivity Applied to Chemistry", John Wiley, New York, 1951, p. 121.
7. Purkayastha and Bhattacharya, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 871.

of the guest ion. The same thing has been observed here in the case of scandium where pyrophosphates are well known to form complex ions in solution⁸. We could not go beyond this range due to paucity of natural scandium.

The uptake of scandium and thorium by zirconium and ceric pyrophosphates was studied up to a finite concentration of the tracer ion. The limiting concentration, where the value took a diminishing trend, was not, however, studied in each case because of the paucity of natural scandium and the trouble in removing the activity due to thorium and its disintegration products. The conclusion, in general, can be arrived at that thorium and scandium are taken up by zirconium and ceric pyrophosphate both at finite and at tracer concentrations of the guest ion through mixed crystal formation. Scandium, however, differs in this case from thorium because of its tervalency. In this case we can assume an anomalous mixed crystal formation. But Ce(IV), thorium, and zirconium are all tetravalent and from this study we can arrive at the conclusion that pyrophosphates of tetravalent elements are morphologically analogous. It will not be out of place to mention that it has not been possible to study the homogeneous distribution factor (D)⁹ on the anticipation that the pyrophosphate may undergo hydrolysis if it is allowed to equilibrate for a long time to achieve exchange through diffusion and recrystallisation process necessary for homogeneous distribution law.

Incidentally, it is another example of the application of radioactive isotopes where morphological analogy can be shown by simple co-separation studies.

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Received August 8, 1963.

8. Yatsimersky and Vasilev, "Instability Constant of Complex Compounds", Pergamon Press, 1960,
9. Henderson and Krack, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 738,